

PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AND WELL-BEING IN PROSTHETIC USERS

THE ROLE OF REALISM IN BELOW-KNEE PROSTHESES

Stefania Sansoni

✉ stefania.sansoni@strath.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

The needs of below-knee amputees, in terms of the aesthetics of their prostheses, receive little or no attention. Failure to address this issue could create dissatisfaction with the body image of amputees. This paper seeks to explore different aspects of the psychological issues and well-being of users by focusing on the hypothesis that the level of realism in prostheses is linked to multiple factors, i.e. the time elapsed since amputation and acceptance of limb loss. Specifically, we highlight the positive role of using artificial-looking devices for promoting the self-confidence of wearers during the second phase post-amputation, and the use of cosmetic devices in the first phase. The data derives from a closed ended questionnaire, email exchanges with users and an in-depth literature review. The paper constitutes a contribution to research on the “aesthetics of prosthetic devices” by taking into account the dynamics behind the psychological distress and well-being of prosthetic users.

KEYWORDS: prosthetic devices, aesthetics, well-being, body image, lower limb amputees

INTRODUCTION

This paper explores the role of realism in prostheses as a way of meeting the expectations of prosthetic users at two stages post-amputation, and how wearing the “right” design (according to the perception of the amputee observer) can positively affect body image and self-esteem. Specifically, we argue for the positive role played by non-realistic prostheses in enhancing psychological well-being.

“Prosthetic” is a term that refers to devices designed to replace a missing part of the body. This definition applies to devices that replace a limb segment rather than externally-applied devices which are referred to as “orthotics”. For example, an artificial arm, leg, or finger can be classified as a “prosthesis”, whereas external entities such as a dental brace, insoles or a pair of glasses are “orthotics”. Specifically, our field of research currently focuses on below-knee prosthetic devices. In this paper we will refer to any device resembling the appearance of a human leg with the term “cosmetic” (Figures 1a and 1b), while the terms “non-cosmetic”,

“non-realistic” or “artificial looking” will be used identify devices with an interface dissimilar to a human leg (Figures 1c and 1d).

The subjects of our research are amputees [or rather people who have had a limb amputated (Pearsall, 1999)] who are prosthetics users or future users. For the specific purposes of this paper we refer to below-knee amputees, even though the sample does include a few examples of upper limb wearers.

The limited literature on the aesthetics of prosthetic devices demonstrates that this field is still in its infancy. A review of current prosthetic design literature shows that to date extended work has been largely focused on the technical improvement of the devices (Cheetham, Suter, & Jäncke, 2011; Hahl, Taya, & Saito, 2000; Klute, Kallfelz, & Czerniecki, 2001; Mak, Zhang, & Boone, 2001) in spite of the research around aesthetics. Our search found few academic studies discussing realistic-appearance prosthetic devices- and that the literature that does exist focuses mainly on upper limb designs (Davies, Douglas, & Small, 1977; Ferrone, 2001). This contrasts with a considerable number of companies (e.g. “Pro-

Figure 1: cosmetic devices with high (a) and medium (b) level of human resemblance (sources: (a) The Alternative Limb Project, photographer: Rosemary Williams - www.thealternativelimbproject.com - (b) photo from personal archive), and “non-cosmetic” or “artificial looking” devices (c and d) (sources (c) The Alternative Limb Project, photographer: Rosemary Williams - www.thealternativelimbproject.com - (d) “Ecko Unltd. Prosthetic Leg” of Jordan Diatlo - <http://www.jordandiatlo.com>)

cosil”, “Touch Bionics”, “The alternative Limb project”, “Otto-bock”) and associations (i.e. “Amputee Coalition”, “Amputee prosthetics”, “Westcoast brace and limbs”) that deal with the production and/or advertisement of high-level realistic-looking limbs. Similarly, we found little literature investigating the aesthetics of non-realistic devices (Capestany & Esparza, 2011; Hilhorst, 2004; Plettenburg, 2005), but wider attention on the part of companies (e.g. “The alternative Limb project”, “Bespoke innovations”) and designers (i.e. Sophie de Oliveira Barata, Scott Summit).

METHOD

The main data-sources used to prepare this paper consist of responses to a questionnaire, personal e-mails from below-knee prosthetic users and a comprehensive literature review.

Regarding the internet survey, the study consisted of an online questionnaire (that took approximately 25 minutes to complete). It was based on a set of closed ended questions structured using the Likert scale rating system. A quantitative method was adopted because of the necessity of collecting a large amount of data. There were one hundred and fourteen participants in the study who may be classified as follows:

- Amputation: Amputees 24 (21.1%) and Non-amputees 90 (78.9%)
- Gender: 40.4% Male and 59.6% Female

Amputee participants were sub-classified into: lower limb amputees 22 (92%) and upper limb amputees 2 (8%).

The International Personality Item Pool (IPIP) template was chosen for testing personality aspects (L. R. Goldberg et al., 2006). This system provides a list of questions for investigating the personality traits of participants. Each question offered participants the opportunity to rate the statement, choosing one of the five points on the Likert scale between “very inaccurate” and “very accurate”. The scoring had to be

evaluated as “positive” or “negative” according to the statement proposed. The issues investigated were: level of physical activity, extroversion and assertiveness, sociability, calmness, courage, kindness, and generosity. Each of these traits was tested by posing an average of 10 questions.

Regarding the e-mail based data collection, the information was gained through informal conversations engaged in with prosthetic users between 2012 and 2013.

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROSTHETIC USERS

The amputation of a limb can generate unpleasant psychological consequences (R. T. Goldberg, 1984; Horgan & MacLachlan, 2004; Price & Fisher, 2007; Rybarczyk, Nyenhuis, Nicholas, Cash, & Kaiser, 1995; Shukla, Sahu, Tripathi, & Gupta, 1982; Whyte & Niven, 2001) in addition to profound effects on body image (Maguire & Parkes, 1998). Specifically, the literature shows how dealing with the new bodily dissatisfaction can generate symptoms such as stress and depression (Breakey, 1997; Cansever, Uzun, Yildiz, Ates, & Atesalp, 2003; Williamson, Schulz, Bridges, & Behan, 1994), difficulty in accepting an amputation (Sjödahl, Gard, & Jarnlo, 2004) and problems establishing romantic and sexual relationships (C. Murray, 2009). In some cases it has been shown that an amputee experiences extreme denial. English (1989) records the example of a woman amputee who “had even left instructions in her will that she should be buried in her artificial leg so that even beyond the grave her secret would be preserved”.

Breakey (1997) argues that, despite the existence of psychological issues influencing psychological well-being and life satisfaction in amputees, the rehabilitation process pays little attention to these problems in patients. Additionally, Asano et al. (2008) state that, according to their scale, lower limb amputees record lower quality of life scores than upper limb amputees.

The literature shows that the physical trauma of amputation can have negative psychological repercussions in amputees, and we argue that it is important to account for this if the prosthetic users are to be better understood.

Surprisingly, in addition to these examples illustrating the negative issues associated with amputation, it has also been shown that positive post-amputation experiences exist. Many experts in the field, including medical staff, tend to conceive of amputation as a “mutilating” procedure, while other researchers see the issue in a positive light, as a process of reconstruction (Bowker, 1981; Bradway, Malone, Racy, Leal, & Poole, 1984). Stress is one of the main consequences of limb amputation. However it has been argued that when this aspect is overcome, it can have a positive outcome as the self-esteem of the amputee can be “strengthened and grown” [(Ickovics & Park, 1998), in (Oaksford, Frude, & Cuddihy, 2005a)]. Similarly, Bonanno (2004) describes the experience of coping with adversity (i.e. amputation) as an opportunity to thrive and change. In accordance with this belief, Gallagher and Maclachlan (2001) report an interview with an amputee who states she’s feeling “great” because she managed to “get on with her life” by dealing successfully with the trauma and now feels like “a better person”.

Tedeschi et al. (1996) state that the experience of thriving after a traumatic experience is named “posttraumatic growth” and that this process is obtained by a change in how people view themselves (Tedeschi & Calhoun, [1996, 2004]), cited in Phelps et al. (2008), when others highlight the importance of “meaning-making” for successfully overcoming the post-traumatic experience (Taylor, 1983). Phelps et al. (2008) argue that the core process of thriving positively with amputation consists in engaging a set of cognitive coping strategies such as revising life goals and priorities if the traumatic experience is to be overcome. An amputee mentioned in Gallagher and Maclachlan (2001) stated that the acceptance of amputation is an important issue in the process of getting over the experience [the psychological dissatisfaction]: “it is like when somebody you know dies, it takes a while to get over it, but gradually you do”.

In accordance with the literature, our questionnaire shows that amputees (compared with non-amputee participants) recorded a significantly higher “positive level of traits” showing a “positive attitude towards life” such as: physical activity, extroversion (or assertiveness), sociability, bravery (or courage), and generosity. Our understanding of the psychological process post-amputation is that amputees, after facing the natural process of negative psychological reactions, can respond to psychological distress and reach a positive life-facing attitude, even gaining higher levels than non-amputees. We claim that both negative and positive psychological feelings in amputees are part of their normal process of “growth” and that these can be directly related to prosthetic design choices. Consequently, gaining a clear comprehension of these dynamics is essential if the role of the aesthetics of devices for wearers is to be understood. This belief will be explored further in the following sections.

The grieving process post-amputation

In “psychological adaption to amputation”, Bradway et al. (1984) argue for the existence of one pre-amputation stage (which may not occur in certain cases) and three post-amputation stages, which is universally experienced. The stages are a) grief b) realization that the limb is no longer present c) denial and d) return home. The authors state that denial is the stage where people tend to show negative psychological symptoms (depression, insecurity, worry, etc.) (Friedmann, 1978; Parkes, 1975), and that the phase of returning home can generate either a successful adaption to disability or, sadly, a “fall” back to the previous stage.

The prosthetic web site “Hanger” describes amputation as a life-changing experience that may be emotionally devastating. “Everyone deals with these feelings in different ways. Allow yourself to grieve and to feel your loss. [...]. Ultimately, you will reach a stage of acceptance. How long this may take varies from person to person but one thing is certain: when you are able to accept your new body image you’ll be able to lead a happier life.”

“The Five Stages of the Grieving Process” have been identified as a set of psychological stages that people go through when experiencing amputation: denial, anger, bargaining, depression, acceptance and hope (Kubler-Ross, 2009). This process is discussed by the amputee researcher Saul Morris (in “Amputee Coalition”) and is described as “essential” because anyone who has ever experienced an amputation goes through the same cycle, though the duration of each stage varies according to the individual (“some people will do it in a short time, while others will take several months”).

Rybarczyk et al. (1995), show that depression in amputees can be classified both in the long term (17 years after amputation) and in the short term (4 years after amputation). This finding suggests that the grieving process may not necessarily end with “acceptance and hope” and therefore the stages may not hold true for everyone, or that “acceptance and hope” may take even longer than 17 years after amputation.

The role of prosthetic devices in the psychological well-being of prosthetic users

“No-one comes out unscathed by an amputation and a prosthesis may act as a security, a guarantee or a mechanism for requiring the integrity of one’s physical appearance, which validates one’s psychological integrity.” (Pillet & Didierjean-Pillet, 2001)

For some time now researchers have been interested in the enhancement of self-body image and psychological well-being of amputees. Singh, Hunter and Philip (2007) empathize the benefits of learning new skills and improving the mobility of the amputee in order to overcome unpleasant psychological feelings. Similarly, Dunn (1996) focuses on: 1) finding positive meaning in being an amputee, 2) adopting an optimistic attitude and 3) perceiving control over disability. In the context of dealing with phantom limb pain (an issue

that negatively affects the physical and psychological well-being of amputees), it has been argued that factors such as, for example, the individual patient's medical history, phantom sensations, daily activities, social support received and the influence of an amputation has to be taken into account when analyzing improvements in an amputee's well-being (Bosmans et al., 2007).

A functional prosthesis may undoubtedly be considered an important contribution to achieving well-being. For example, it has been argued that the use of a prosthesis helps the user to regain mobility (Pohjolainen, Alaranta, & Kärkäinen, 1990) and to return to performing social activities (C. D. Murray, 2005). However, by going beyond the functional role of the prosthesis, the literature shows how the aesthetics of the device influence the psychological concerns of amputees. It has been argued that if users are to accept a prosthesis it must be comfortable, functional and have a pleasant appearance (Millstein, Heger, & Hunter, 1986). Similarly, Bhuvaneshwar et al. (2007) report that "cosmetic appearance appears to play as great a role in psychological sequel of amputation as does the return of physical function". Similarly, Murray (2005) reports the case of a prosthetic user who refuses to wear his prosthesis on a daily basis, providing as an explanation the judgment that the device is "clumsy and unattractive" rather than a specific complaint regarding functionality. Similarly, Nguyen (2013), and Rybarczyk and Behel (2008) address the fact that adjustment difficulties in amputees should be reconnected to the aesthetics of the limb by highlighting the importance of this kind of aesthetic dissatisfaction for females.

From a design perspective, Cairns, Murray et al. (2013) argue that the appearance of the prosthesis affects acceptance of the device and that there is a link between the perception of its negative aesthetics and a negative self-body image. In the context of lower limb cosmetic devices, the argument goes that the improvement of the aesthetics of the prosthesis can consequently help to improve the self-body image and psychological wellbeing of the wearer. Accordingly, it is our belief that the aesthetics of prosthetics can influence the psychological well-being of lower-limb amputees and we argue that this principle should be accounted for in prosthetic design.

Considering the role of hand prostheses, Pillet and Didierjean-Pillet (2001) argue that the device can be the "answer" to overcoming the issues encountered when taking part in social activities. The authors also highlight the fact that all amputees have special personal requirement and that "nowadays, function is not sought at any cost, especially not at the cost of sacrificing the appearance of the hand". Regarding the use of digital cosmetic prostheses (i.e. devices with a high level of limb-like realism – Figure 1a), Carrol and Fyfe (2004) state that in contrast to PVC prostheses (devices with a lower level of limb-like realism – Figure 1b), they can reduce the level of anxiety and depression in the wearer. Their conclusion is that the "improvement" of the realistic appearance of devices can enhance the well-being of users. We find ourselves discordant with the positive effect of the level of realism in prostheses, but we agree with these authors concern-

ing the importance of pleasant aesthetics in helping resolve psychological distress in amputees.

The limitation that we found in the works cited up till now is that they take into account only the aesthetic role of cosmetic prostheses. Few academic papers have focused on the non-cosmetic aesthetics of prosthetic design when it comes to improving the experiences of the wearers, suggesting that this research gap is relatively new and unexplored. An example of literature which does briefly touch upon the subject is provided by authors such as Capestany and Esparza (2011) who describe a case study of an amputee who required a personalized golf-prosthesis. In a similar manner, Plettenburg (2005) designed a prosthetic prehensor (a design similar to a wrench) for children, by using a combination of solid design and an appealing colorful style. Similarly, Hilhorst (2004) described his non-conformist-styled design applied to prostheses for children, personalizing them for each individual's unique "identity". These three examples are significant in terms of exploring the role of non-cosmetic-looking devices intended to enhance the well-being of individuals. Our research differs in that it examines both cosmetic and non-cosmetic designs and that it focuses on lower limb devices rather than upper limbs.

Regarding upper limb amputees, Pillet (2001) proposes the question "can a patient who abandons his/her prostheses be considered healed?". According to our point of view, in upper limb prosthetic users this stage of acceptance of the new body could be verified if the amputee chooses to use a non-cosmetic device or to abandon the use of prosthetics altogether. As a matter of fact, the difference between upper and lower limb amputees is that the use of a prosthetic leg may be required if mobility is to be regained, or the individual is to be able to take part in social activities; in these cases arm/hand prostheses mainly represent an aesthetic "security" (Pillet, 1984). However, considering that this paper focuses on lower limb prosthetic users, we will not go into this issue in greater depth here.

LEVELS OF REALISM IN PROSTHESES REFLECTING THE ACCEPTANCE OF AMPUTATION

Our opinion is that the achievement of well-being for amputees is not a simple goal but is linked to internal dynamics and external events correlated to the trauma of the amputation. Additionally, all individuals have a personal story and the track for achieving well-being may vary from case to case. However, it is our belief that a set of general dynamics may potentially be present in all subjects. In addition to the important role of issues such as the rehabilitation process, medical treatment, social support, etc., the role played by the aesthetics of prosthetics can make a valid contribution that enhances well-being in amputees by improving their self-body image.

In this section we introduce our hypothesis regarding the role of realism in the aesthetics of prostheses in enhancing acceptance

Figure 2. Graph showing the two phases experienced by prosthetic users for the desirable level of realism in the prostheses related to influencing factors - Phase 1: the amputated body is not accepted and the preference is for cosmetic devices, Phase 2: positive acceptance of amputation and attraction of non-cosmetic devices

during the post-amputation stages, with an additional focus on other factors involved (i.e. time and coping strategies).

First, we propose a simplistic division of the post-amputation period into two stages: the first characterized by strong unpleasant psychological feelings (“Phase one”) correlated with the fact that the limb loss is not accepted yet, and the second stage during which a positive attitude towards life emerges as a consequence of a greater acceptance of amputation (“Phase two”). Second, we aim to correlate an overview of the aesthetic needs of prosthetic users in order to determine a desirable level of realism in the prostheses (Figure 2).

We understand the psychological process during the post-amputation period to be far more complex and that it may normally include more than two phases. However, in order to meet the specific requirements of this research, we decided to simplify the post-amputation stage and to focus only on the factors of non-acceptance [i.e. grouping the first four phases of the “grieving process”: denial, anger, bargaining, and depression (Kubler-Ross, 2009)] and acceptance [i.e. the last phase of the “grieving process”: acceptance and hope (Kubler-Ross, 2009)].

The main factors affecting the phases of the graph are Time, Level of Acceptance of Amputation, and Personal Characteristics (gender, age, self-consciousness). The first and second factors (Time and Level of Acceptance) will be described first, after which we will deal with Personal Characteristics.

Time

Sprangers and Schwartz (1999) suggest that the internal standards of amputees are re-defined over time, and that psychological adaptation occurs in a parallel process (Gallagher & MacLachlan, 2001; Livneh, Antonak, & Gerhardt, 1999; Pezzin, Dillingham, & MacKenzie, 2000). Additionally,

it has been stated that coping strategies change over time simultaneously with the changing demands of adjustment (Lazarus, 2006 cited in Oaksford et al., 2005a). In a similar manner, Desmond & MacLachlan (2006) state that a short time elapsed since amputation is correlated with high levels of post trauma distress and symptoms of anxiety - a belief shared also by Oaksford et al. (2005a), according to whom a long time since amputation leads to a more favorable adjustment to limitation. This statement is supported by a study suggesting that depression is marked immediately after amputation and gradually resolves over time (Frank et al., 1984). Phelps et al. (2008) argue that, when high levels of depressive disorders are found in the first two years after amputation (25-35%), they subsequently tend to show a significant decline (mean: 8%).

The passage of time post-amputation causes the user to face negative and positive factors such as: anxiety, depression, anger and guilt, perceived prosthetic mobility, social support, partner support, learning new skills, comorbidity, prosthetic problems, social activity (Asano et al., 2008; Bhojak & Nathawat, 1988; Buffery & Gray, 1972; Burger & Marincek, 1997; C. Murray, 2009).

The factors listed do not necessarily appear universally and the lapse of time necessary for people to re-define their own standard varies from case to case. It is proposed that the presence or absence of a given factor can influence the length of time necessary for a person to move from Phase 1 to Phase 2.

Level of Acceptance of Amputation

The “Level of Acceptance of Amputation” is affected by the degree to which factors occurring during the post-amputation period are dealt with positively or negatively (see previ-

ous point), and, according to our point of view, is positively achieved when cognitive coping strategies are successfully applied. Examples of coping strategies are: 1) engaging an active and confrontational attitude rather than a passive and maladaptive one, 2) being optimistic instead of pessimistic 3) being social and “externally-orientated” instead of cognitive and internally-orientated (Livneh, Antonak, & Gerhardt, 2000) 4) reversing life goals and priorities 5) accommodating traumatic experience and 6) seeking beneficial aspects (Phelps et al., 2008). As mentioned in the section “psychological aspects of prosthetic users”, it is also important to acknowledge the role of “meaning-making” (Taylor, 1983) if a successful post-traumatic growth is to occur after amputation (Dunn, 1996; Oaksford, Frude, & Cuddihy, 2005b).

Senra et al. (2012) illustrate the emotional changes that occur in lower limb amputees prior to obtaining a new self-identity (Figure 3). The process described by the authors is directly relevant to our work as it proposes, within the process of self-identity change following amputation, the role of prostheses and the embodiment of amputation as final factors in obtaining a new self-identity. Additionally, their research shows that a set of psychological changes occurs prior to the identity change (i.e. changes in self-in-the present, self-biography, self-projection in the future or self-identification with the impairment). Our research views these factors as a set of “coping strategies”.

Two stages post-amputation

In relation to time and to the level of acceptance of amputation, the phases of our graph are described as follows:

Phase 1. The amputee is subject to unpleasant psychological feelings (Horgan & MacLachlan, 2004; Price & Fisher, 2007; Shukla et al., 1982; Whyte & Niven, 2001) and is attracted to devices resembling the realistic look of a limb (i.e. cosmetic devices) that remind the subject of the lost leg. We believe that people do not accept that they have an amputated body - or at least have no desire to show it to others - as they have not (yet) fully accepted that their body is “altered”. In agreement with Pereira et al. (1996) and Carrol and Fyfe (2004), our belief is that cosmetic prostheses with human-leg resemblance can be considered important in the process of “restoring the person’s damaged body image”. We claim that at this stage attraction towards realistic-looking devices has to be conceived as a normal phase that needs to be navigated before a full acceptance of the amputated body may be gained. It is to be hoped that this phase will not last long.

Phase 2. The amputee gains a better acceptance of their “mutilated” body, the traumatic experience does not generate increased levels of psychological reaction, and the self-body image is more positive. This belief is supported by the fact that our investigation recorded the presence of a percentage of amputees who were attracted to cosmetic devices, in opposition to a smaller number who were attracted to non-cosmetic devices. Individuals no longer feel like hiding the amputation as they did before, and do not fear using a device with non-human characteristics that clearly “shows” the limb loss. Cairns (2013) recorded that 49/59% of patients rating satisfaction with cosmetic prostheses were neutral or dissatisfied with the color/shape/touch and feel of the devices and stated that

Figure 3 Model for self-identity changes related to lower limb amputation (Senra et al., 2012)

a higher level of realism did not generate further aesthetic attraction. When prosthetic users overcome the normal process of psychological distress and regain confidence they will also be ready to go “beyond” the use of a realistic prosthetic. By wearing a non-cosmetic device they find attractive they will, in return, reach higher levels of confidence in their own bodies.

Our hypothesis is that the attraction towards robotic devices (an attraction that does not exclude a parallel favorable attitude towards cosmetic devices) represents an evolution/improvement in the self-body vision of the amputee. We argue that when amputees “accept” their new body shape they are psychologically more confident and consequently do not see their disability as a visual limitation they need to “hide” using a realistic silicone cosmetic device. The point of view of John (screen-name), a male amputee, is that:

“Although I think that there are lots of reasons you might want a limb that looks lifelike, so many of us acknowledge our loss of a limb and feel that if it is no longer there, why pretend? If it is obviously false, then why not make more of this possible advantage?”

Additionally, we report the words of a male amputee (screen-name: Albert) at an advanced stage of amputation (his amputation having occurred many years ago):

“I have chosen not to hide what I have irreversibly lost. I do not care about this issue (the loss), but it does not occur to me to falsify something that is not reproducible with “silicone”[...]. I could not tolerate the surprise of the people when, as will obviously happen, they discover the deception. No. I prefer to show immediately what has been lost and that it has been replaced by something that does not create feelings of pity but, I hope, aesthetic attraction.”

Albert is not afraid of showing his disability and feels the desire to wear a device that represents aesthetic needs involving a big step beyond the attractions of cosmesis. He is ready to use a prosthesis that does not merely resemble the old limb, or else a device designed to represent an important meaning for the wearer such as “strength”, “speed”, “gracefulness”, “playfulness”. He also hopes the device will generate aesthetic appreciation in external observers as well.

In agreement with this statement, we report the evidence of John:

“I lost my leg – below the knee - when I was 16 [he is currently 45] and until recently I have 'made do' with what was out there, usually something that looked like it had been taken from a shop mannequin. [...] A couple of years back I came across a robotic-looking leg. This style is so appealing that now I shorts in the gym when I'm wearing it. It looks 'cool!' It suggests I am healthy, active, sporty: everything my mannequin leg doesn't!”

In “Design meets Disability” Pullin (2009) argues that prostheses should not merely become replacements of the human limb, as instead their design helps determine and communicate simply what they are. Additionally, he mentions work to apply artistic values to upper limb design, reporting the point of view of the sculptor Jacques Monestier: “I wanted

to transmute what might be considered a disfigurement into something marvelous and exotic. I wanted to create a hand that would no longer cause shame and repulsion. I wanted the amputee to be proud to have it and look at it. And for the people around the amputee, I wanted the prosthetic hand to be an object of healthy curiosity, a work of art”.

Our belief, which matches the points of view reported above, is that the use of a non-cosmetic device may help wearers to see their own bodies as something that is more than an “illusion” of what existed before and is now lost forever. Amputees have the “power” to choose a pleasant looking product design and to show external observers that they are not disabled but, rather, super-abled individuals who are proud of their bodies.

As we mentioned above, attraction and the use of non-cosmetic devices does not imply that all users should deny the use of cosmetic devices for good. We wish only to declare that they should be seen as one option (e.g. for combining with a dress, or for a formal occasion) that can add to the confidence gained by wearing non-cosmetic devices on other occasions. The top fashion model Aimee Mullins, a double amputee, states: “I don't have any issue wearing legs that aren't human-like, but I want the option to have human-looking legs” [“Two legs good, 24 legs better” (Vainshtein, 2012)]. Aimee is the perfect example of a person who has coped well with limb loss and reached a high level of confidence with her body image. We would consider her to be living in Phase 2.

FUTURE WORK

In order to test our hypothesis on the attraction of realism in devices, we have initiated an interview-based experiment based on a revised version of the RGT technique (a method taken from Personal Construct Psychology). The experiment shows the amputee participants a set of non-cosmetic and cosmetic devices and records their level of attraction towards the different levels of realism. The non-cosmetic devices include a set of our own designs that embody a set of principles and elements, as well as meanings (i.e. “stability”, “energy”, “gracefulness”, “lightness” etc.). The aim of the experiment is to compare the level of attraction towards realistic prosthetics among participants with different characteristics such as 1) length of time since amputation 2) gender 3) age 4) personal characteristics / background. Our hope is that the investigation will confirm the arguments advanced in this study.

CONCLUSION

Our belief is that prostheses that are perceived as attractive by prosthetic wearers can improve their body image and psychological well-being. Additionally, the development of acceptance for the new body can influence the attraction felt towards realistic or non-realistic-looking designs. We argue

that prosthetic devices with non-human characteristics can better promote the acceptance of limb loss and provide well-being to the user during a second, post-amputation, phase. Furthermore we argue that cosmetic devices can help wearers to deal with the psychological adjustments associated with limb loss only during the first phase. The hypothesis has been conceived in general terms because, for instance, the length of time needed to arrive at Phase 2 may vary from person to person according to the particular history of each amputee, and there are likely to be many people who might be considered “exceptions”.

This work aims to contribute to academic research on the aesthetics of prosthetic devices and to relate this concept to the promotion of the psychological well-being of prosthetics users. We advance a different perspective regarding the aesthetic needs of amputees, relating this issue to their post-amputation psychological processes. Additionally, we show why the aesthetics of prosthetic devices should receive more attention in the post-amputation rehabilitation process, in order to promote improved self-body image among amputees.

REFERENCES

- Amputee Coalition. Retrived February 9, 2014, from www.amputee-coalition.org/military-instep/cosmesis.html
- Amputee Prosthetics. Retrived February 9, 2014, from www.amputeeprosthetist.com/prosthetic-prosthesis/cosmesis-realistic-artificial-limbs-and-realistic-prosthetics
- Asano, M., Rushton, P., Miller, W. C., & Deathe, B. A. (2008). Predictors of quality of life among individuals who have a lower limb amputation. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 32(2), 231-243.
- Bespoke innovations. Retrived February 9, 2014, from www.bespokeinnovations.com
- Bhajak, M. M., & Nathawat, S. S. (1988). Body image, hopelessness and personality dimensions in lower limb amputees. *Indian journal of psychiatry*, 30(2), 161-165.
- Bhuvanewar, C. G., Epstein, L. A., & Stern, T. A. (2007). Reactions to Amputation: recognition and treatment. *Primary care companion to the Journal of clinical psychiatry*, 9(4), 303.
- Bonanno, G. A. (2004). Loss, trauma, and human resilience: Have we underestimated the human capacity to thrive after extremely aversive events? *American psychologist*, 59(1), 20.
- Bosmans, J. C., Suurmeijer, T. P. B. M., Hulsink, M., van der Schans, C. P., Geertzen, J. H. B., & Dijkstra, P. U. (2007). Amputation, phantom pain and subjective well-being: a qualitative study. *International Journal of Rehabilitation Research*, 30(1), 1-8. doi:10.1097/MRR.1090b1013e328012c328953.
- Bowker, J. H. (1981). Amputee rehabilitation: critical factors in outcome. *The Journal of the Arkansas Medical Society*, 78(5), 181-183.
- Bradway, J. K., Malone, J. M., Racy, J., Leal, J., & Poole, J. (1984). Psychological adaptation to amputation: An overview. *Orthotics and Prosthetics*, 38(3), 46-50.
- Breakey, J. W. (1997). Body image: the lower-limb amputee. *JPO: Journal of Prosthetics and Orthotics*, 9(2), 58-66.
- Buffery, A. W. H., & Gray, J. A. (1972). *Sex differences in the development of spacial and linguistic skills*. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone.
- Burger, H., & Marincek, C. (1997). The life style of young persons after lower limb amputation caused by injury. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 21(1), 35-39.
- Cairns, N., Murray, K., Corney, J., & McFadyen, A. (2013). Satisfaction with cosmesis and priorities for cosmesis design reported by lower limb amputees in the United Kingdom: Instrument development and results. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 0309364613512149.
- Cansever, A., Uzun, O., Yildiz, C., Ates, A., & Atesalp, A. S. (2003). Depression in men with traumatic lower part amputation: a comparison to men with surgical lower part amputation. *Military medicine*.
- Capectany, L., & Esparza, W. (2011). Transhumeral Recreational Prosthesis. *Journal of Prosthetics and Orthotics*, 23(3), 165-167.
- Carroll, Á. M., & Fyfe, N. (2004). A comparison of the effect of the aesthetics of digital cosmetic prostheses on body image and well-being. *JPO: Journal of Prosthetics and Orthotics*, 16(2), 66-68.
- Cheetham, M., Suter, P., & Jäncke, L. (2011). The human likeness dimension of the “uncanny valley hypothesis”: behavioral and functional MRI findings. *Frontiers in human neuroscience*, 5.
- Davies, E., Douglas, W., & Small, A. (1977). A cosmetic functional hand incorporating a silicone rubber cosmetic glove. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 1(2), 89-93.
- Desmond, D. M., & MacLachlan, M. (2006). Coping strategies as predictors of psychosocial adaptation in a sample of elderly veterans with acquired lower limb amputations. *Social science & medicine*, 62(1), 208-216.
- Dunn, D. S. (1996). Well-being following amputation: Salutary effects of positive meaning, optimism, and control. *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 41(4), 285.
- English, A. (1989). PERSONAL VIEW Psychology of limb loss. *BMJ*, 299, 1287.
- Ferrone, T. (2001). Methods for making prosthetic surfaces: Google Patents.
- Frank, R. G., Kashani, J. H., Kashani, S. R., Wonderlich, S., Umlauf, R. L., & Ashkanazi, G. S. (1984). Psychological response to amputation as a function of age and time since amputation. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 144(5), 493-497.
- Friedmann, L. W. (1978). *The psychological rehabilitation of the amputee*: Charles C Thomas.
- Gallagher, P., & Maclachlan, M. (2001). Adjustment to an artificial limb: a qualitative perspective. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 6(1), 85-100.
- Goldberg, L. R., Johnson, J. A., Eber, H. W., Hogan, R., Ashton, M. C., Cloninger, C. R., & Gough, H. G. (2006). The international personality item pool and the future of public-domain personality measures. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 40(1), 84-96. doi:10.1016/j.jrp.2005.08.007

- Goldberg, R. T. (1984). New trends in the rehabilitation of lower extremity amputees. *Rehabilitation literature*.
- Hahl, J., Taya, M., & Saito, M. (2000). Optimization of mass-produced trans-tibial prosthesis made of pultruded fiber reinforced plastic. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 285(1-2), 91-98. doi: 10.1016/S0921-5093(00)00720-6
- Hilhorst, M. (2004). 'Prosthetic fit': On personal identity and the value of bodily difference. *Medicine, health care, and philosophy*, 7(3), 303-310
- Horgan, O., & MacLachlan, M. (2004). Psychosocial adjustment to lower-limb amputation: A review. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 26(14-15), 837-850. doi: doi:10.1080/09638280410001708869
- Ickovics, J. R., & Park, C. L. (1998). Paradigm shift: Why a focus on health is important. *Journal of Social Issues*, 54(2), 237-244.
- Klute, G. K., Kallfelz, C. F., & Czerniecki, J. M. (2001). Mechanical properties of prosthetic limbs: adapting to the patient. *Journal of rehabilitation research and development*, 38(3), 299.
- Kubler-Ross, E. (2009). *On death and dying: What the dying have to teach doctors, nurses, clergy and their own families*: Taylor & Francis US.
- Lazarus, R. S. (2006). *Stress and emotion: A new synthesis*: Springer Publishing Company.
- Livneh, H., Antonak, R. F., & Gerhardt, J. (1999). Psychosocial adaptation to amputation: the role of sociodemographic variables, disability-related factors and coping strategies. *International Journal of Rehabilitation Research*, 22(1), 21-32.
- Livneh, H., Antonak, R. F., & Gerhardt, J. (2000). Multidimensional investigation of the structure of coping among people with amputations. *Psychosomatics*, 41(3), 235-244.
- Maguire, P., & Parkes, C. M. (1998). Coping with loss: Surgery and loss of body parts. *British Medical Journal*, 316(7137), 1086-1088. doi: 10.1136/bmj.316.7137.1086
- Mak, A. F., Zhang, M., & Boone, D. A. (2001). State-of-the-art research in lower-limb prosthetic biomechanics-socket interface: a review. 38(2).
- Millstein, S., Heger, H., & Hunter, G. (1986). Prosthetic use in adult upper limb amputees: a comparison of the body powered and electrically powered prostheses. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 10(1), 27-34.
- Monestier, J., Retrived February 9, 2014, from <http://www.jacques-monestier.com/en/>
- Morris, S. (2008), Retrived February 9. From http://www.amputee-coalition.org/first_step_2003/psychological-aspects-amputation.ht
- Murray, C. (2009). *Amputation, prosthesis use, and phantom limb pain [Internet resource] : an interdisciplinary perspective*: New York ; London : Springer.
- Murray, C. D. (2005). The social meanings of prosthesis use. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 10(3), 425-441.
- Nguyen, D. D. (2013). *The beauty of prostheses: designing for female amputees*. Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- Oaksford, K., Frude, N., & Cuddihy, R. (2005a). Positive Coping and Stress-Related Psychological Growth Following Lower Limb Amputation. *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 50(3), 266-277. doi: 10.1037/0090-5550.50.3.266
- Oaksford, K., Frude, N., & Cuddihy, R. (2005b). Positive Coping and Stress-Related Psychological Growth Following Lower Limb Amputation. *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 50(3), 266.
- Oliveira Barata, S. in "The Atlantic". Retrived February 9, 2014, from www.theatlantic.com/health/archive/2014/01/the-art-of-designer-artificial-limbs/282800/
- Ottobock. Retrieved February 9, 2014, from www.ottobockus.com
- Parkes, C. M. (1975). Psycho-social transitions: comparison between reactions to loss of a limb and loss of a spouse. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 127(3), 204-210.
- Pearsall, J. (1999). The concise Oxford dictionary. In P. Judy (Ed.): Oxford England ; New York : Oxford University Press.
- Pereira, B. P., Kour, A.-K., Leow, E.-L., & Pho, R. W. H. (1996). Benefits and use of digital prostheses. *The Journal of Hand Surgery*, 21(2), 222-228. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0363-5023\(96\)80104-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0363-5023(96)80104-3)
- Pezzin, L. E., Dillingham, T. R., & MacKenzie, E. J. (2000). Rehabilitation and the long-term outcomes of persons with trauma-related amputations. *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation*, 81(3), 292-300.
- Phelps, L. F., Williams, R. M., Raichle, K. A., Turner, A. P., & Ehde, D. M. (2008). The importance of cognitive processing to adjustment in the 1st year following amputation. *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 53(1), 28.
- Pillet, J. (1984). Appareillage esthétique de la main mutilée. *Les Mutilations de la Main. Paris: Expansion Scientifique Francaise, GEM Monographie*(13), 224-228.
- Pillet, J., & Didierjean-Pillet, A. (2001). Aesthetic hand prosthesis: gadget or therapy? Presentation of a new classification. *Journal of Hand Surgery (British and European Volume)*, 26(6), 523-528.
- Plettenburg, D. H. (2005). The Wilmer Appealing Prehensor. *JPO Journal of Prosthetics and Orthotics*, 18(2), 43-45.
- Pohjolainen, T., Alaranta, H., & Kärkäinen, M. (1990). Prosthetic use and functional and social outcome following major lower limb amputation. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 14(2), 75-79. doi: 10.3109/03093649009080326
- Price, E. M., & Fisher, K. (2007). Further Study of the Emotional Needs of Amputees. *JPO Journal of Prosthetics and Orthotics*, 19(4), 106-108.
- Procosil. Retrived February 9, 2014, from www.procosil.com
- Pullin, G. (2009). *Design meets disability*: Mit Press.
- Rybarczyk, B., & Behel, J. (2008). Limb loss and body image Psycho-prosthetics (pp. 23-31): Springer.
- Rybarczyk, B., Nyenhuis, D. L., Nicholas, J. J., Cash, S. M., & Kaiser, J. (1995). Body image, perceived social stigma, and the prediction of psychosocial adjustment to leg amputation. *Rehabilitation Psychology*, 40(2), 95.

- Senra, H., Oliveira, R. A., Leal, I., & Vieira, C. (2012). Beyond the body image: a qualitative study on how adults experience lower limb amputation. *Clinical rehabilitation*, 26(2), 180-191.
- Shukla, G. D., Sahu, S. C., Tripathi, R. P., & Gupta, D. K. (1982). A psychiatric study of amputees. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 141(JUL), 50-53. doi: 10.1192/bjp.141.1.50
- Singh, R., Hunter, J., & Philip, A. (2007). The rapid resolution of depression and anxiety symptoms after lower limb amputation. *Clinical rehabilitation*, 21(8), 754-759.
- Sjödahl, C., Gard, G., & Jarnlo, G.-B. (2004). Coping after transfemoral amputation due to trauma or tumour—a phenomenological approach. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 26(14-15), 851-861. doi: 10.1080/09638280410001662996
- Sprangers, M. A., & Schwartz, C. E. (1999). Integrating response shift into health-related quality of life research: a theoretical model. *Social science & medicine*, 48(11), 1507-1515.
- Summit, S. Retrieved February 9, 2014, from www.imgur.com/gallery/28pJN
- Taylor, S. E. (1983). Adjustment to threatening events: A theory of cognitive adaptation. *American psychologist*, 38(11), 1161.
- Tedeschi, R. G., & Calhoun, L. G. (1996). The Posttraumatic Growth Inventory: Measuring the positive legacy of trauma. *Journal of traumatic stress*, 9(3), 455-471.
- Tedeschi, R. G., & Calhoun, L. G. (2004). " Posttraumatic Growth: Conceptual Foundations and Empirical Evidence". *Psychological inquiry*, 15(1), 1-18.
- The alternative Limb project. Retrieved February 9, 2014, from www.thealternativelimbproject.com
- Touch Bionics. Retrieved February 9, 2014, from www.touchbionics.com
- Vainshtein, O. (2012). "I Have a Suitcase Just Full of Legs Because I Need Options for Different Clothing": Accessorizing Bodyscapes. [Article]. *Fashion Theory-the Journal of Dress Body & Culture*, 16(2), 139-169. doi: 10.2752/175174112X13274987924014
- Westcoast brace and limbs. Retrieved February 9, 2014, from www.wcbl.com/prosthetics-2/newest-technologies/silicone-prosthetics
- Whyte, A. S., & Niven, C. A. (2001). Psychological Distress in Amputees with Phantom Limb Pain. *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management*, 22(5), 938-946. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0885-3924\(01\)00352-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0885-3924(01)00352-9)
- Williamson, G. M., Schulz, R., Bridges, M. W., & Behan, A. M. (1994). Social and psychological factors in adjustment to limb amputation. *Journal of Social Behavior & Personality*.